

Spiritual Well-Being and Work-Related Stressors of Teachers in Relation to Their Teaching Performance

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Abstract:

This descriptive study examined the level of spiritual well-being and level of work-related stressors of teachers in relation to their teaching performance in one of the Districts in a medium-sized school Division in a highly urbanized City in Central Philippines during the school year 2023-2024. A quantitative design gathered the data from 196 teachers. Using the descriptive and inferential analyses, the results revealed that the teachers' spiritual well-being was at high level and obtained a moderate level of work-related stressors. Also, there was a high level of spiritual well-being in the areas/dimensions of religious and existential well-being. Likewise, there was a high level of work-related stressors in the area of professional responsibilities. At the same time, there was only a moderate level of work-related stressors in the areas of work environment and students' conflict. Meanwhile, the level of teachers' performance during the school year 2022 – 2023 was outstanding. Whereas no significant difference exists in the level of spiritual well-being and in the level of work-related stressors. Likewise, no significant difference was shown in the level of teachers' performance. No significant relationship was shown between the level of the spiritual well-being of teachers and their level of teaching performance. Finally, a significant relationship exists between the level of work-related stressors of teachers and their level of teaching performance.

Keywords: Educational Management, Spiritual Well-Being and Work-Related Stressors, Descriptive, Philippines

Introduction:

Background of the Study

We are spiritual beings at our very core. There are many different perspectives on spirituality, ranging from the traditional understanding of spirituality as an expression of religiosity and a search for the sacred to a humanistic perspective of spirituality devoid of religion (Kontrimienė, 2019). As Paul et al. (2020) described, "spirituality of teachers is important to the educational system because it acts as a compass for the teaching-learning process in the classroom, where students can cultivate positive interpersonal relationships. However, the teaching profession is inherently stressful, and stress of any kind directly affects teachers' behavior with students and, in turn, shapes the personalities of future generations. Hence, the inclusion of spirituality in this section is important and influential in eliminating stress-provoking factors from the workplace by changing the situation. Meanwhile, teachers' job performance can be defined as the predictable value that a teacher has to carry out over a standard period. Furthermore, low workplace spirituality for teachers' sporadically causes conflict and stress, which affects their performance.

With nearly a decade in service, the researcher observed that teachers nowadays are compromised by their secularistic, dispiritedness, and materialistic mindsets, which also depreciate their spirituality (Mahipalan & Sheena, 2019). Corollary to the previous observations, teachers view specific issues in life and so on as not merely a decline in morality and changing religiosity. But it is also a product of their being critical of what they should believe and practice in response to social and cultural changes around them (Chirico et al., 2020). These phenomena are not even new, and the number of work-related assignments given to teachers is still overwhelming. Teachers have limited opportunities to attend wellness programs, spiritual lectures, and mindfulness meditation classes like team-building activities incorporating spiritual components in the workplace, which greatly affect their spiritual well-being.

Despite the anxiety and its detrimental effects, there have also been numerous reports about hope, or the conviction in one's capacity to act and find solutions to problems (Javanmardifard et al., 2020). This knowledge gap is

particularly intriguing because both constructs may co-occur within an individual when faced with a challenging situation. Although study into work-related stressors has been a universal move, limited study is currently available about Spiritual well-being and work-related stressors of teachers in relation to their teaching performance.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed in determining the level of spiritual well-being and work-related stressors of teachers in relation to their teaching performance.

Literature Review:

Spiritual Well-being of Teachers. According to Sumagpao (2022), the teachers' workplace spirituality and Organizational Citizen Behavior were based on their understanding of themselves and others, such as working together to resolve conflicts and caring about their own and others' spiritual health. Furthermore, incorporating and transferring spiritual values into the classroom will encourage instructors to be more humane (Gupta, 2020).

Work-related Stressors of Teachers. Teaching has been identified as a high-stress profession and is frequently regarded as psychologically and socially demanding (Herman et al., 2018; Kwon et al., 2022; Lam & Wong, 2017). Therefore, one of the most important things an educator can do is monitor stress levels at work. Teachers may experience stress from their regular work activities, which could impair their effectiveness. The following list of stressors is comprised of 1) laborious tasks, 2) overwork, 3) approaching due dates, 4) juggling multiple tasks, 5) unreasonable task assignment.

Teacher's performance. A teacher's performance is a key indicator of an educational institution's success. Improving teacher quality must be a priority for improving education. Teacher performance does not improve independently; it must be identified, facilitated, devolved, and maintained to meet objectives. Teachers want not only recognition for their efforts but also peace of mind in the workplace (Qudus et al., 2021). Teachers' performance automatically rises to a high level when they are motivated.

Research Methodology:

This section presents the research design used, the locale, the subjects, respondents of the study, the research instruments, the conduct of the study, the procedure in the analysis of the data relative to the specific objectives and statistical tools used in the study.

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive research design, which determines the level of spiritual well-being and level of work-related stressors of teachers about their teaching performance.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of the study were 196 public secondary school teachers from a total population of three-hundred ninety-eight (398). Since the number of respondents was quite large, stratified sampling and random sampling techniques were used, and the Cochran formula was used to find the sample size.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Schools	Population (N)	Sample Size (n)	Percentage (%)
A	92	51	23.12
B	179	70	44.97
C	80	40	20.10
D	47	35	11.81
Total	398	196	100%

Validity

The researcher adapted the criteria developed for the evaluation survey questionnaire Carter V. Good and Douglas E. Scates set forth. The interpretation is as follows: Excellent (4.21 – 5.00); Very Good (3.41 - 4.20); Good (2.61 – 3.40); Fair (1.81 – 2.60); Poor (1.00 – 1.80).

The mean rating obtained from the five validators was 4.80, interpreted as excellent. This obtained mean showed that the research instrument was, therefore, valid.

Reliability

Reliability was established through a dry run of 30 teachers in the same district; however, these teachers were not among the actual respondents of this study. A reliability instrument, which is Cronbach's Alpha, was used for the test to be reliable. The researcher administered the test once. To be reliable, the obtained value of the tests between 0.70 and 1.00 is considered "acceptable" in most research situations.

The computed alpha for the level of the spiritual well-being of teachers was 0.851, interpreted as "Good." The level of work-related stressor was 0.948, which is interpreted as "Excellent," making this instrument reliable.

Data-Gathering Procedure

The researcher personally administered the survey to the respondents, explained its purpose, and assisted them in filling out the questionnaire using a Google Form. The researcher secured proper instructions and clearly explained the objectives of the study and the terms and items contained in the instruments so that respondents would fully understand their tasks of answering the tests. The data gathered from the responses of the respondents was tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The raw data was transformed into numerical code guided by a coding manual. This allows computer processing, statistical derivations, and tabular presentation. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to process the encoded data in the computer.

Research Ethics Protocol

The researcher ensured the general ethical principles of respect for persons, beneficence, and justice to establish the ethical soundness of the study. The researcher highly ensured that no personal data compromising the respondents' identity was collected in adherence to the Data Privacy Act of 2012, specifically on the access to the data both by the researcher and the analyst. The respondents were assured that no information disclosing their identity was released or published without their consent to the said disclosure, except when necessary to protect their rights and welfare.

Analytical Schemes

In the data analysis, various procedures were employed depending on the study's objectives.

Objective No. 1 used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, length of service, average family monthly income, and civil status.

Objective No. 2 used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine teachers' spiritual well-being level according to the following areas: Religious Well-being and Existential Well-being.

Objective No. 3 also used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of work-related stressors of teachers according to the following areas: Professional Responsibilities, Work Environment, and Students Conflict.

Objective No. 4 also used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine teachers' spiritual well-being level when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 5 used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of work-related stressors of teachers when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 6 used the descriptive analytical scheme to determine the level of teachers' performance during the School Year 2022-2023 when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 7 used the comparative analytical scheme to determine the significant difference in teachers' spiritual well-being level when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 8 also used the comparative analytical scheme to determine the significant difference in teachers' work-related stressors level when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 9 used the comparative analytical scheme to determine the significant difference in teachers' teaching performance level when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 10 used the relational analytical scheme to determine the significant relationship between the level of spiritual well-being of teachers and their level of performance.

Objective No. 11 also used the relational analytical scheme to determine the significant relationship between the level of work-related stressors of teachers and their level of performance.

Statistical Tools

Various statistical tools were employed to analyze the data, depending on the objectives of the study. Objective No. 1 used the frequency count and percentage to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, length of service, average family monthly income, and civil status. A percentage frequency distribution is a display of data that specifies the percentage of observations that exist for each data point or grouping of data points. It is a particularly useful method of expressing the relative frequency of survey responses and other data. Objective No. 2 used the Mean to determine the level of spiritual well-being of teachers according to the following areas: Religious Well-being and Existential Well-being. The statistical mean has a wide range of applicability in various types of experimentation. This type of calculation eliminates random errors and helps to derive a more accurate result than a result derived from a single experiment. The statistical mean can also be used to interpret statistical data. Some important properties make statistical mean very useful for measuring central tendency.

The Scale of Interpretation for the Overall Spiritual Well-Being

Range Score	Verbal Interpretation
20 – 40	reflects a sense of low overall spiritual well-being.
41 – 99	reflects a sense of moderate spiritual well-being.
100 – 120	reflects a sense of high spiritual well-being.

The scale of Interpretation for the Religious Well-Being

Range Score	Verbal Interpretation
A score of 50-60	A positive view of one's relationship with God
A score of 21-49	Moderate sense of religious well-being
A score of 10-20	Unsatisfactory relationship with God

The Scale of Interpretation for the Existential Well-Being

Range Score	Verbal Interpretation
A score of 50-60	High level of life satisfaction with one's life and a clear sense of purpose
A score of 21-49	Moderate level of life satisfaction and Purpose
A score of 10-20	Low satisfaction with one's life and possible lack of clarity about one's purpose in life

Objective No. 3 used the Mean to determine the level of work-related stressors of teachers according to the following areas: Job Demand, Teaching Environment and Students Conflict.

The mean scores were be interpreted as follows:

Range Score	Verbal Interpretation
4.50 - 5.00	Very High Level
3.50 - 4.49	High Level
2.50 – 3.49	Moderate Level
1.50 – 2.49	Low Level
1.00 – 1.49	Very Low Level

Objective No. 4 used the Mean to determine teachers' spiritual well-being level when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 5 used the Mean to determine the level of work-related stressors of teachers when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 6 used the Mean to determine the level of teachers' performance during the school year 2022-2023 when grouped according to the aforementioned variables.

The level of teachers' performance was measured based on the DepEd IPCRF rating as follows:

Range Score	Verbal Interpretation
4.50-5.00	Outstanding
3.50-4.49	Very Satisfactory
3.50-4.49	Satisfactory
1.50-2.49	Unsatisfactory
Below 1.49	Poor

Objective No. 7 used the Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant difference in teachers' spiritual well-being level when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

The Mann-Whitney U test compares differences between two independent groups when the dependent variable is ordinal or continuous but not normally distributed. The Mann-Whitney U test is a popular nonparametric test to compare outcomes between two independent groups. The Mann-Whitney U test, sometimes called the Mann-Whitney Wilcoxon Test or the Wilcoxon Rank Sum Test, is used to test whether two samples are likely to derive from the same population (i.e., that the two populations have the same shape). Some investigators interpret this test as comparing the medians between the two populations. Recall that the parametric test compares the means ($H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$) between independent groups. If the p -value is below the usually agreed alpha risk of 5 percent (0.05), the null hypothesis can be rejected, and at least one significant difference can be assumed. The computed p -value was interpreted by utilizing the approach of rejecting the null hypothesis if the p -value is less than or equal to 0.05 level of significance and accepting the null hypothesis if the p -value is greater than 0.05 level of significance.

Objective No. 8 also used the Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant difference in the level of work-related stressors of teachers when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 9 used the Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant difference in the level of teaching performance of teachers when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Objective No. 10 used the Spearman rho to determine the significant relationship between the level of spiritual well-being of teachers and their level of performance.

A Spearman correlation coefficient is also referred to as Spearman rank correlation or Spearman's rho. It is typically denoted either with the Greek letter rho (ρ) or r_s . Like all correlation coefficients, Spearman's rho measures the strength of association between two variables. As such, the Spearman correlation coefficient is similar to the Pearson correlation coefficient.

Finally, the computation of the p -value will be interpreted using the following guide: Reject the null hypothesis if the p -value is equal to or less than 0.05 level of significance or accept the null hypothesis if the p -value is greater than 0.05 level of significance.

Objective No. 11 also used the Spearman rho to determine the significant relationship between the level of work-related stressors of teachers and their level of performance.

Findings and Discussion:

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made by following certain appropriate procedures to give the exact data and solution to each problem.

Profile of the respondents in terms of the following variables: Age, Sex, Highest Educational Attainment, Length of Service, and Average Family Monthly Income

Table 2

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 40 years old)	94	48.00
	Older (40 years old and above)	102	52.00
Sex	Male	62	31.60
	Female	134	68.40
Highest Attainment	Educational Lower (Bachelor's Degree)	136	69.40
	Higher (Master's/Doctoral Degree)	60	30.60
Length of Service	Shorter (below 7 years)	97	49.50
	Longer (7 years and above)	99	50.50
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower (below Php 30,000)	50	25.50
	Higher (Php 30,000 and above)	146	74.50
Civil Status	Single	78	39.80
	Married	118	60.20
Total		196	100.00

Profile of Respondents

As shown in the table, there were 196 respondents in the study. In terms of age, 94 or 48.00 % are younger respondents, and 102 or 52.00% are older respondents. As to sex, male respondents were 62 or 31.60%, while female respondents were 134 or 68.40%. Regarding the highest educational attainment, 136 or 69.40% of respondents had lower educational attainment, and 60 or 30.60% of respondents had higher educational attainment. Regarding the length of service, there were 97 or 49.50% of respondents in a shorter length of service, and there were 99 or 50.50% of respondents in a longer length of service. Regarding the average family monthly income, 50 or 25.50% were teachers who belonged to lower income, while 146 or 74.50% were teachers who belonged to higher income. As to Civil Status, there were 78 or 39.80% of respondents with single status and 118 or 60.20% of married ones.

This implies that the majority of the teachers are older, most of them need to advance and hold a bachelor's degree in education, and nearly all of the educational fields are clearly female-dominated. Also, based on the given data, almost entirely, teachers are in longer lengths of service and are largely married. The data also shows a predominantly higher average family monthly income.

Level of Spiritual Well-Being of Teachers when grouped according to the Area of Religious and Existential Well-being

Table 3

Level of Spiritual Well-Being of Teachers in the Area of Religious and Existential Well-being

Areas	Mean	Interpretation
1. Religious Well-Being	57.79	High level
2. Existential Well-Being	55.34	High level
Overall Mean	56.56	High level

The table shows that the level of the spiritual well-being of teachers in the area of religious and existential well-being achieved a high-level result. Moreover, the area of religious well-being obtained a mean score of 57.79, interpreted as a high level. Meanwhile, the area of existential well-being garnered a mean score of 55.34, also interpreted as a high level.

This means that though it was at a high-level interpretation, existential well-being was found to be the teachers' lowest area/dimension, possibly because some teachers are not fully aware of the path they want to undergo in life. The assessment could also be influenced by different factors that compromise their disposition in life. Also, when faced with adversity, there are some teachers who are unsatisfied with their work, and they are flooded and bombarded with a lot of paperwork to be accomplished on time. They tend to reflect more intensely upon existential issues such as the meaning and purpose.

The findings conform to Liang et al. (2023) study on the Relationship among Workplace Spirituality, Meaning in Life, and Psychological Well-being of Teachers, which revealed that one's sense of meaning in life or existential well-being has a great impact to the teachers considering how much paperwork they must complete on time, some teachers are not satisfied with their jobs.

Level of Work-Related Stressors of Teachers in the Area of Professional Responsibilities, Work Environment, and Students' Conflicts

Table 4

Level of Work-Related Stressors of Teachers in the Area of Professional Responsibilities

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I get stressed in...		
1. preparing lesson plans and daily logs of activities, including appropriate, adequate, and updated instructional materials	3.68	High Level
2. participating and contributing to the school learning continuity plan during the planning and implementation process	3.57	High Level
3. attending numerous seminars, workshops, and trainings.	3.34	Moderate Level
4. beating the deadlines required by the nature of their job	3.72	High Level
5. monitoring and evaluating pupils/students' progress	3.71	High Level
6. preparing materials for classroom observation	3.85	High Level
7. pursuing post-graduate studies to earn more knowledge.	3.55	High Level
8. managing time and workload efficiently	3.69	High Level
Overall Mean	3.64	High Level

The table presents an overall mean score of 3.64, interpreted as high level. Item No. 3, which states "attending numerous seminars, workshops, and training," got the lowest mean score of 3.34, interpreted as a moderate level. Meanwhile, Item No. 6, which states "preparing materials for classroom observation," got the highest mean score of 3.85, interpreted as high level.

As a result, factors such as the preparation of materials and classroom observation may cause teachers to be burdened and stressed. This could be because there are some who are not prepared due to inefficient time and workloads. Other reasons could also be attributed to financial constraints and the need for more learning materials.

This conforms to the study of Auman and Asuncion (2023), which states that factors such as the preparation of materials and classroom observation itself may cause burden and stress to teachers. In comparison to other professionals, teachers also reported heavier workloads. It appears that being under a lot of stress is bad for teachers' health.

Table 5
Level of Work-Related Stressors of Teachers in the Area of Work Environment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I get stressed in...		
1. the availability of technological tools required for teaching-learning at home	3.42	Moderate Level
2. looking for available instructional devices such as projector, TV, or audio-visual equipment	3.51	High Level
3. an immediate evaluation or monitoring of a superior	3.39	Moderate Level
4. dealing with discrimination and bullying situations in the workplace	3.25	Moderate Level
5. maintaining harmonious relationship with fellow teachers and other school personnel as well as with parents and other stakeholders.	3.05	Moderate Level
6. maintaining a tidy and orderly classroom	3.36	Moderate Level
7. working with parents and other stakeholders to help resolve classroom/school issues.	3.24	Moderate Level
8. finding refreshments and preparing for the next classes.	3.07	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.29	Moderate Level

The table shows an overall mean score of 3.29, interpreted as a moderate level. Item No. 5, which states "maintaining a harmonious relationship with fellow teachers and other school personnel as well as with parents and other stakeholders," got the lowest mean score of 3.05, interpreted as a moderate level. Meanwhile, Item No. 2, which states "looking for available instructional devices such as projector, TV or audio-visual equipment," got the highest mean score of 3.51, interpreted as high level.

This implies that teachers' highest work-related stressor was looking for available instructional devices such as a projector, TV, or audio-visual equipment, maybe because the instructional devices in their schools are limited only, and some can't afford them due to financial incapacity. Teachers already knew the significance of instructional devices, especially in the process of learning, and they found them to be very effective in improving students' interest and achievement in education. Although the working conditions of the schools and the resources transferred to the schools are similar in general, schools may differ when factors such as the number of students, school management, and school environment.

The results aligned with Maffea's (2020) assertion that schools face financial challenges in providing new laptops for every student. Consequently, educators must devise strategies to make up for this shortfall in the classroom. If they run out of textbooks, they may use a projector to let the students view the teacher's screen. Teachers may become stressed out due to a lack of resources in the classroom.

Table 6
Level of Work-Related Stressors of Teachers in the Area of Students' Conflicts

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a teacher, I get stressed in...		
1. managing students' problem behavior inside the classroom.	3.29	Moderate Level
2. teaching students who are poorly motivated.	3.33	Moderate Level
3. investigating the problem in the students' dispute in order to come up with a workable solution	3.27	Moderate Level
4. student's absences and tardiness	3.59	High Level
5. employing strategies to deal with students' attitudes about schoolwork, their own work, or the work of others.	3.41	Moderate Level
6. building a harmonious relationship with the students	2.98	Moderate Level
7. addressing all students' concerns	3.21	Moderate Level
8. negotiating and adopting a give-and-take approach to problem situations.	3.09	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.28	Moderate Level

Based on the table, the overall mean score is 3.28, interpreted as a moderate level. Item No. 6, which states "building a harmonious relationship with the students," got the lowest mean score of 2.98, interpreted as a moderate level. Meanwhile, Item No. 4, which states "student's absences and tardiness," got the highest mean score of 3.59, interpreted as high level.

This implies that students' absences and tardiness give the teachers a high level of stress, which could be attributed to tardiness disrupting the learning of other students in their classes. Teachers can become frustrated as late students disrupt instruction, often requiring reteaching of what they have missed.

The findings parallel the Akkuş and Çinkir (2022) study, which revealed that due to absent students' learning deficiencies, classroom management becomes challenging for teachers, and schools stray from their objectives. Time spent on absenteeism-related procedures made teachers face difficult situations in classroom management.

Level of Spiritual Well-Being of Teachers When Grouped According to the Aforementioned Variables

Table 7

Level of Spiritual Well-Being of Teachers in the Area of Religious and Existential Well-being When Grouped According to Age

Areas	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Religious Well-Being	57.72	High Level	57.84	High Level
2. Existential Well-Being	54.95	High Level	55.71	High Level
Overall Mean	56.34	High Level	56.77	High Level

Based on the table presented, it can be gleaned that the overall mean scores were 56.34 for the younger group and 56.77 for the older group; both were interpreted as high level. For the younger group, the highest area is religious well-being, with a score of 57.72, interpreted as a high level. The area of existential well-being was the lowest, with a score of 54.95, which is interpreted as a high level. The Same goes for the older group. The highest area is religious well-being, with a score of 57.84, interpreted as a high level, and the area of existential well-being was the lowest, with a score of 54.95, interpreted as a high level.

Existential well-being dimension/area was rated to be the lowest, though it has a high-level interpretation as shown above; this indicates that there are teachers younger or older who do not have a clear view of a peaceful and satisfying life, possibly because certain variables such as an excessive workload, job difficulty, excessive pressure, and increased overtime hours affects them.

The findings conform to Saratian et al. (2019) study that overwork has negative effects that include emotional reactions as well as physical and mental exhaustion. An excessive workload can contribute to teachers being unsatisfied and even cause stress at work.

Table 8

Level of Spiritual Well-Being of Teachers in the Area of Religious and Existential Well-being When Grouped According to Sex

Areas	Male		Female	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Religious Well-Being	57.72	High Level	57.72	High Level
2. Existential Well-Being	55.27	High Level	55.37	High Level
Overall Mean	56.60	High Level	56.55	High Level

Generally, based on the table, it can be gleaned that the overall mean scores were 56.60 for the male group and 56.55 for the female group; both were interpreted as high level. For the male group, the highest area is religious well-being, with a score of 57.72, interpreted as a high level. At the same time, the area of existential well-being was the lowest, with a score of 55.27, interpreted as a high level. The same goes for the female group, whose highest area is religious well-being, with a score of 57.72, interpreted as high level, and the area of existential well-being was the lowest, with a score of 55.37, interpreted as high level.

It is inferred that both male and female teachers rated existential well-being as the lowest, though it was at a high-level interpretation. This result could be attributed to the fact that they shoulder many administrative duties, which affect their life satisfaction. In addition, these teachers are highly dissatisfied due to poor working conditions and lack of autonomy.

The findings conform to Namupala's (2023) study, where teachers find their work dissatisfactory or unenjoyable due to poor working conditions and a lack of autonomy.

Table 9

Level of Spiritual Well-Being of Teachers in the Area of Religious and Existential Well-being When Grouped According to Highest Educational Attainment

Areas	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Religious Well-Being	57.96	High Level	57.38	High Level
2. Existential Well-Being	55.09	High Level	55.92	High Level
Overall Mean	56.53	High Level	56.65	High Level

Data shows that the overall mean scores were 56.53 for respondents in the lower group and 56.65 for respondents in the higher group; both were interpreted as high level. For respondents in the lower group, the highest area is religious well-being, with a score of 57.96, interpreted as a high level. The area of existential well-being was the lowest, with a score of 55.09, which is interpreted as a high level. The same goes for the respondents in the higher group, whose highest area is religious well-being, with a score of 57.38, interpreted as high level, and the area of existential well-being was the lowest, with a score of 55.92, interpreted as high level.

The findings indicate that both groups' lowest score was in the area of existential well-being. Though it was at a high level, there are some who are possibly unsatisfied with their work, maybe because of salary and reports to be submitted ASAP. They may lose motivation, and their outlook on life may become negative.

The findings conform to Akomolafe and Ogunmakin (2014), who found that teachers' work-life is at the core of their general lives. When they are unhappy with their jobs, it generally affects their lives. They may lose motivation, and their outlook on life may become negative. The reverse is true when they are fulfilled and happy with their jobs. The result of this study has provided further evidence that job satisfaction and life satisfaction are closely related.

Table 10

Level of Spiritual Well-Being of Teachers in the Area of Religious and Existential Well-being When Grouped According to Length of Service

Areas	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Religious Well-Being	57.89	High Level	57.69	High Level
2. Existential Well-Being	55.46	High Level	55.22	High Level
Overall Mean	56.68	High Level	56.45	High Level

The table depicts the overall mean scores of 56.68 for respondents with shorter lengths of service and 56.45 for longer lengths of service; both were interpreted as high levels. For respondents with a shorter length of service, the highest area is religious well-being, with a score of 57.89, interpreted as a high level. At the same time, the area of existential well-being was the lowest, with a score of 55.46, interpreted as a high level. The same goes for the respondents with a longer service length. The highest area is religious well-being, with a score of 57.69, interpreted as a high level, and the area of existential well-being was the lowest, with a score of 55.22, interpreted as a high level.

The findings indicate that existential well-being is rated to be the lowest yet at a high-level interpretation, possibly because there are teachers who are not fully satisfied with their jobs because of the bulk of workloads. Some teachers find or feel their work is not meaningful because they are not supported or appreciated, which may also affect their overall life satisfaction.

The findings are parallel to those of Lavy (2022), who are not fully satisfied with their work; hence, sometimes they tend to lose their sense of meaning at work. The reasons behind this are heavy workload, student misbehavior, and lack of administrative support.

Table 11

Level of Spiritual Well-Being of Teachers in the Area of Religious and Existential Well-being When Grouped According to Average Family Monthly Income

Areas	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. Religious Well-Being	57.24	High Level	57.97	High Level
2. Existential Well-Being	54.10	High Level	55.76	High Level
Overall Mean	55.67	High Level	56.87	High Level

The result shows the overall mean scores of 55.67 for respondents with lower income and 56.87 for respondents with higher income; both were interpreted as high level. For respondents with lower income, the highest area is religious well-being, with a score of 57.24, interpreted as a high level. At the same time, the area of existential well-being was the lowest, with a score of 54.10, interpreted as a high level. The same goes for the respondents with higher income, with the highest area being religious well-being, with a score of 57.97, interpreted as high level, and the area of existential well-being was the lowest, with a score of 55.76, interpreted as high level.

From the above presentation, it can be gleaned that both groups' lowest scores in the area/dimension of existential well-being, possibly because there were teachers who were unsatisfied with their work due to workloads and insufficient time for the reports to be submitted. They tend to have negative attitudes and their thoughts about the work they do affect the quality and efficiency of teaching.

The findings concur with Kumar's (2015) study on the Influence of Spirituality on Burnout and Job Satisfaction in Oman. The findings of the research indicated that some teachers expressed dissatisfaction with their work, which could be attributed to heavy workloads. The effectiveness of their teaching is impacted by their negative attitudes and beliefs about the work they accomplish.

Conclusion:

Though teachers obtained high-level results, they are still experiencing challenges, particularly regarding existential well-being. Determinants in causing work-related stress among teachers are in the area of Professional responsibilities. The majority of the teachers perceived that they had a high level of spiritual well-being. However, the area of existential well-being being the lowest means that there are items that have something to do with their work satisfaction. Meanwhile, teachers perceived their work-related stress as moderate or high regarding line items when grouped according to their demographic variables. Hence, there are contributing factors in the areas of Professional responsibilities, work environment, and student conflict, which cause a lot of stress to the teachers. The teachers were very efficient in their work, as disclosed by their IPCRF rating, which is at an outstanding level. The difference in the areas of religious and existential in the level of spiritual well-being of teachers was insignificant. There is no significant connection between teachers' demographics and professional responsibilities, work environment, and students' conflict.

The difference in teachers' profile and their teaching performance was insignificant. The level of spiritual well-being of teachers does not have a significant relationship with their teaching performance. The level of teachers' work-related stressors and the level of teachers' performance do have a significant relationship.

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